

Successive cancellation decoding of polar codes using new hybrid processing element

Sujanth Roy James, Lakshminarayanan Gopalakrishnan

Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering National Institute of Technology Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India

Article Info

Article history:

Received Dec 29, 2021

Revised Feb 17, 2022

Accepted Mar 11, 2022

Keywords:

ASIC

Channel coding

Decoder

FPGA architecture

Polar code

Successive cancellation

ABSTRACT

Polar codes are one of the best linear block codes that are capacity achieving and incorporating along with it a simplified encoding and decoding routines. Successive cancellation (SC) algorithm is one of the predominantly used decoding algorithms due to its low complexity. It has broad scopes for hardware architecture design and reformulation. For polar code, the trade-off among the long latency and the silicon area of the SC algorithm is a bottleneck for the design of a high throughput polar decoder. The available prior SC polar decoder designs have higher area requirements for higher block length. This paper introduces a unique reformulation of the processing element (PE) block of SC decoding. The proposed reformulation leads to two benefits: firstly, critical path and hardware complexity of the PE are meaningfully reduced by using a unified adder block. Secondly, the silicon area requirement and the power consumption were also reduced considerably without any loss in performance. The proposed PE is used to build the decoder for various block lengths. Moreover, a Gate-level analysis of the proposed decoder has revealed that the design attains an 18% area reduction and 38% reduction in power consumption over the conventional one with similar performance.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Sujanth Roy James

Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering

National Institute of Technology Tiruchirappalli

Tanjore Main Road, NH67, near BHEL, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu 620015, India

Email: sujanthroyj@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Errors owing to interference, device reparations, and arbitrary noise corrupt the actual data stream before they reach the receiver end. These errors need to be corrected before they are used at the receiver end. Channel coding techniques helps to minimize the errors and rectify them appropriately to reconstruct the original data. Channel coding primarily modifies the original data stream at the transmitter to minimize the error occurrence and reverts them at the receiver end to reconstruct the original signal. The term encoding denotes the operations at the transmitter and decoding indicates the processes at the receiver, respectively. The prime focus is to develop high-performance channel codes with adequately low complexity that diminishes the impact of errors in a communication system. This allows timely, practical implementation into the silicon technology of the day.

Proposed by E Arıkan, the polar codes stand as one of the finest capacity-achieving codes having low encoding and decoding complexity of the order $O(N \log N)$, where N is the code length [1]. Polar codes function on blocks of bits and are therefore classified under the block code family. Polar codes are established on a recursive concatenation of the short core functions that convert physical channels to virtual channels. As the virtual channel count increases, they tend to have either low reliability or high reliability i.e.,

they polarize. This feature enables the message bits to be allotted to the most reliable channel. Erdal Arikan put forth the first version of capacity achieving error correcting codes (ECC) for binary-input discrete memoryless channel [1]. Since then polar codes have emerged as one of the prominent model. Polar codes are known for their exceptional encoding and decoding architecture which have low complexity and recursive structure. They are constructed based on channel polarization, where message bits are transmitted through the most reliable channel [1]. The widely used successive cancellation decoder (SCD) has an attractive architecture with low hardware complexity of the order $O(N \log N)$, where N is the block length.

Several architectures have been proposed for the successive cancellation decoder (SCD). In SCD, there are three major blocks, including the processing element (PE), partial sum generation unit (PSG) and memory unit (MU). In this work, an area-efficient architecture for the PE and hence the decoder is proposed. An architectural modification has been carried out on the PE, which reduces the overall area to a great extent. SCD is the widely used algorithm that can assure exceptional error-correcting performance in polar code decoding. The hardware architectures of the conventional SCD occupies a large silicon area. Improvements in polar decoding techniques and systems are eagerly awaited by the 5G telecommunication industry, where even more complex systems are being developed that require less power, area and obtain high throughput and speed. The challenge in the 5G wireless system is to produce a suitable channel coding scheme to ensemble increasing spectral efficiency. Research in SCD has been going on recently, and therefore, it is worthwhile to come out with a new architecture for the same.

The original version of SCD was proposed in [1] and since then the derivative versions of the same decoder has emerged with improved performance. In spite of the availability of other decoding schemes, the SCD stands unique with its simple architecture easy construction. Yuan et al. had implemented a two bit low-latency polar decoder by using reformulation technique [2]. Leroux et al. had used scheduling and allocation method to reduce the hardware complexity of the decoder [3]. The logarithmic implementation [3], [4] significantly reduced the hardware complexity. The unrolled architecture proposed by Giard et al. has produced a high-throughput in the decoder [5]. A novel merged processing element for SCD based on one's complement was proposed in [6] which helped to increase the throughput. In [7], a Novel simplified merged processing element (SMPE) architecture was proposed for SCD, and the decoding tree was constructed with low complexity. The SCD has the greatest throughput and energy per bit [8] compared to other decoders. Polar codes have been verified to be capacity achieving for binary-input symmetric memoryless channels [9]. The combinational logic based SCD produced a low-power performance [10]. A non-recursive method to create a decoding schedule without affecting the performance has been portrayed in [11].

In [12], path splitting selection (PSS) strategy aided decoder was proposed to lessen the decoding complexity with negotiable performance loss. Based on PSS, two schemes were suggested to locate flawed information bits more precisely. Apart from the PE and PSG, the memory unit is another sub-block that can be optimized according to the requirement [13]. The PE operates with log-likelihood ratio (LLR) instead of likelihood ratio (LR). Hence, polar codes are preferred over the low-density parity-check codes (LDPC) on wireless communication channels due to their better performance [14]. There are rate-less polar code implementations [15], [16] where the number of frozen bits varies based on the information bits' length. This feature provides the extendibility of the decoder for various code rates [17]. Polar codes are extended to non-identically distributed channels and they were found to be capacity achieving but the latency and complexity were sacrificed [18].

Captivatingly, the 5G standardization process of the 3rd generation partnership project (3GPP) has preferred polar codes as the channel coding structure. Therefore, it is clear that different architectural modifications have been proposed on the conventional SC approach to improve its performance like increased throughput, low power, etc. In that way, this paper presents a reduced area SCD with low power consumption. On careful examination of the 2-bit SCD [2], it was eminent that the functioning of the g node in the PE comprises of addition and subtraction performed in parallel and one of the output is chosen based on the previously decoded bit of the f node in the PE. It is clear that one among these is an unwanted operation and can be suitably eliminated. The idea to eliminate the idle branch of the decoding tree prospered to removing the subtraction operation from the PE and carrying out the same with the existing adder. The hybrid processing element proposed here is used to build the SCD. Further, gate optimization is also carried out in the proposed decoder and a noticeable improvement was achieved. The total area of the decoder was reduced by 18%, and the power was reduced by 38% compared with existing recent architectures. During this research, the functionality of the SCD was the same as the original proposed SCD in [1].

The remaining paper is arranged as follows: Section 2 highlights polar codes' encoding and decoding process and the proposed system design consisting of the proposed hybrid processing element and the decoder. Section 3 deliberates the implementation results, and the paper is concluded in section 4.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

Polar codes fall under the banner of linear block codes and are one of the available forward error correction (FEC) codes. They have low computational complexity and are capacity-achieving codes. Polar codes with rate $R=I/N$ have a code length of $N=2^n$, and I ($0 \leq I \leq N$) denotes the number of information bits, whereas $N-I$ denotes the number of frozen bits added to the information bits. The construction of polar codes follows a very simpler approach compared to other traditional approaches like turbo codes. Encoding occurs in the transmitter end, where the channel would be polarized into reliable and unreliable channels. The information bits would be transmitted on the I most reliable channels and the remaining $N-I$ channels stand frozen and are set to 0.

2.1. Polar code-encoding

The encoding approach of polar codes as the (1) [3].

$$x_1^N = u_1^N G_N = u_1^N B_N F^{\otimes n} = u_1^N F^{\otimes n} B_N \quad (1)$$

where $G_N = B_N F^{\otimes n}$ denotes the generator matrix, $F = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$, $(\cdot)^{\otimes n}$ represents the n th Kronecker power,

B_N denotes the bit reversal vector, the input vector represented as $u_1^N = u_1, u_2, \dots, u_N$ having I information bits and $(N-I)$ frozen bits. Also, $x_1^N = x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N$ represents the encoded value [12]. The position of frozen bits are identified by the method explained in [4]. The generator matrix for $N=8$ is given as (2) and (3).

$$G_8 = B_8 F^{\otimes 3} \quad (2)$$

$$G_8 = B_8 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Once G_N is available, the input vector is encoded and prepared for transmission. For rate $R = 0.5$, the number of information bits will be equal to the number of frozen bits.

2.2. Polar code-decoding

The decoding approach is carried out with the widely used Successive Cancellation decoding algorithm [19], [20]. In the decoding scheme, the information bits $u_1^N = u_1, u_2, \dots, u_N$ are retrieved sequentially from the received vector $y_1^N = y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N$. The output bits at stage t can be decoded by processing the LLR function as (4) and (5).

$$u_i = O(LL(i, t)) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where, } u_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } LL(i, t) < 0 \text{ and when } i \text{ is free} \\ 0, & \text{if } LL(i, t) \geq 0 \text{ and when } i \text{ is frozen} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Both encoder and decoder facilitate well-ordered processing configurations and appropriate module sharing owing to their recursive build. Every stage is composed of the kernels f and g appropriately scheduled to decode the data. The f and g kernels function based on (6) and (7).

$$f = \text{sign}(c) \text{sign}(d) \min(|c|, |d|) \quad (6)$$

$$g = c(-1)^{\hat{u}_{sum}} + d \tag{7}$$

where \hat{u}_{sum} decides between addition and subtraction in the kernel g , c and d represent the LLR inputs. \hat{u}_{sum} represents the partial sum of the subset of previously decoded bits. The Conventional decoding tree is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conventional decoding tree

In Figure 1 the highlighted path is the decoding path for bit \hat{u}_1 . This takes three clock cycles. The calculation of \hat{u}_2 occurs in the next clock cycle through the corresponding g kernel which operates with $\hat{u}_{sum} = \hat{u}_2$. At the end of 14 cycles $u_1 - u_8$ are decoded. The decoding schedule for a code block length of 8 is presented in Table 1. Thus the conventional SCD takes $2N-2$ clock cycles to solve a code of length N [1]. Po *et al.* [21] proposed a polar code decoder with variable R and N .

Table 1. Decoding schedule of the conventional SCD for $N=8$

Clock cycle	Stage			Output
	S1	S2	S3	
1	f			
2		f		
3			f	\hat{u}_1
4			g	\hat{u}_2
5		g		
6			f	\hat{u}_3
7			g	\hat{u}_4
8	g			
9		f		
10			f	\hat{u}_5
11			g	\hat{u}_6
12		g		
13			f	\hat{u}_7
14			g	\hat{u}_8

2.3. Proposed new hybrid processing element

The proposed decoder has an area optimized unique scheme of combinational logic that functions to eliminate the unnecessary subtraction operation carried out in the PEs. The proposed PE is termed new hybrid processing element (NHPE), which is used to design the decoder. The conventional SCD has the f node and g node that form the decoder's processing element and are scheduled appropriately to form the decoding tree. After the development of the merged processing element, the f and g operations are selected using a control signal and the decoding tree is constructed accordingly. The research for better-merged processing continued and evolved into 2b-SC decoding, 2b overlapped SC decoder, 2b precomputation decoder and so on [2]. The architectures are optimized for area, power, speed and better architectures were produced. This paper proposes a novel area-optimized processing element with low power consumption compared with the existing processing elements.

On careful examination of the merged processing element in [2], it was noted that during the g node operation, both addition and subtraction are performed in all the iterations. But for the successful functioning of the decoder, only one operation is sufficient and it is decided by the partial sum of the previously decoded bits as (7). The proposed NHPE uses a unique scheme of combinational logic to eliminate the subtraction operation throughout the entire architecture along with a 2x1 multiplexer that chooses between addition and subtraction. This modification in the NHPE is reflected in the whole decoder. In the proposed scheme, the f node operates in the conventional way with the sign and magnitude processed separately. The proposed modification is effected in the g node operation. As soon as the f node is executed, the partial sum is generated which triggers the adder of the g node through the combinational block of XOR gate. When subtraction is to be performed, the sign bit of LLR(d) is negated and addition is performed. Table 2 shows the truth-table for the proposed idea.

Table 2. Truth table of the proposed scheme

Sign of d	Value of \hat{u}_{sum}	Operation to be performed	Modified sign of LLR(d)
Positive (0)	0	Addition	0
Negative (1)	0	Addition	1
Positive (0)	1	Subtraction	1
Negative (1)	1	Subtraction	0

The following example explains the operation.

```

If  $\hat{u}_{sum} = 0$ , i.e. Addition to be performed.
Let's take  $c = +3$  and  $d = -5$ .
Sign rep(c) = 0 0011, Sign rep (d) = 1 0101
New Signed bit (d) = Ex-OR of Previous sign bit (d) and  $\hat{u}_{sum} = (1, 0) = 1$ 
Now 2s_comp_rep(c) = 0 0011,
2s_comp_rep(modified d) = 1 1011,
Now  $c+d = 1 1110$ . Sign(c+d) = 1 0010 i.e -2.
If  $\hat{u}_{sum} = 1$ , i.e. subtraction to be performed.
Let's take  $c = +3$  and  $d = -5$ .
Sign rep(c) = 0 0011, Sign rep (d) = 1 0101
New Signed bit (d) = Ex-OR of Previous sign bit (d) and  $\hat{u}_{sum} = (1, 1) = 0$ .
modified d = 0 0101.
Now 2s_comp_rep (c) = 0 0011,
2s_comp_rep(modified d) = 0 0101,
Now  $a+b = 0 1000$ . Sign (a+b) = 0 1000 i.e 8.

```

The above examples suitably explain Table 1, thus eliminating the subtraction and multiplexer operations successfully. The NHPE is shown in Figure 2. The architecture clearly shows that the subtraction operation is eliminated and a hybrid processing element is proposed.

Figure 2. Proposed processing element-NHPE

2.4. Proposed SCD based on NHPE

The proposed NHPE is used to build the decoder. The proposed modifications in the NHPE when realized in the entire decoder has a greater impact. In stage 1, all the PEs work as f node in the first cycle. In the second cycle, all the PEs of stage 2 are f nodes, and in the third cycle, the PE in stage 3 decodes the output message bits. This is the decoding sequence of the decoder and this process takes a total of $(1.5N-2)$ clock cycles. When pipelining is introduced in this process, the decoding latency can be further reduced by a few cycles. Pipelining is introduced between the stages to speed up the entire decoding process. When pipelining is introduced, the decoding latency can be reduced from $1.5N-2$ to $N-1$ cycles. The f node has a delay of $T_f = 0.709ns$, whereas the g node has a delay of $T_g = 1.86ns$. The other delays involved are $T_{mux} = 0.136ns$ and $T_{xor} = 0.148ns$. In stage 3, once the f node completes its operation, partial sum value, \hat{u}_{sum} is updated, which completes the execution of the g node. The decoding tree for a block length of 8 is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Proposed SC decoder for block length 8

The use of less complex processing element (NHPE) has resulted in reducing the overall complexity of the decoder. The area and power have been reduced considerably in the proposed decoder. The decoding

schedule of the proposed decoder is shown in Table 3. NHPE(f) denotes the proposed processing element functioning in f mode and NHPE(g) denotes the proposed processing element functioning in g mode. The proposed scheduling enables the decoder to complete the process in 7 cycles. Thus, the proposed NHPE not only reduces the on-chip area but also reduces the latency of the decoder.

Table 3. Decoding schedule of the proposed SCD for N=8

Clock cycle	Stage			Output
	S1	S2	S3	
1	NHPE _(f)			
2		NHPE _(f)		
3			NHPE _(f)	\hat{u}_1 and \hat{u}_2
4	NHPE _(g)		NHPE _(g)	\hat{u}_3 and \hat{u}_4
5		NHPE _(g)		
6			NHPE _(f)	\hat{u}_5 and \hat{u}_6
7			NHPE _(g)	\hat{u}_7 and \hat{u}_8

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed SCD was modelled in Verilog HDL, implemented in Xilinx xc7vx980t FPGA and synthesized in Cadence 45nm CMOS technology. The proposed NHPE was used to construct the decoding tree and the decoder was tested upto a code length of 1024. A code rate of 0.5 was used in the design. The proposed model's area and power compared to the existing models [4], [22] are given below in Table 4 and 5. Considerable area and power reduction was achieved in the decoder architecture when the proposed NHPE was used. The functionality of the decoder was unaltered in the proposed architecture. In Table 4 it is emphasized that the area of the proposed model was reduced by at least 16.5% on average.

Table 4. Proposed SCD area comparison report using TSMC 45nm technology

Block length (N)	Area, μm^2			Reduction (%)
	Yuan and Parhi [4]	Zhang and Parhi [22]	Proposed	
8	966.718	3621	8	966.718
64	13917.83	30141	64	13917.83
128	31980.37	60899	128	31980.37
256	72258.24	121925	256	72258.24
512	161123.60	243891	512	161123.60
1024	355478.48	444944	1024	355478.48

Table 5. Proposed SCD power comparison report using TSMC 45nm technology

Block length (N)	Power, μW			Reduction (%)
	Yuan and Parhi [4]	Zhang and Parhi [22]	Proposed	
8	82.02	217.89	49.92	39.133
64	1248.17	1725.03	763.04	38.867
128	2828.38	3567.91	1730.83	38.80
256	6620.32	7049.74	4063.27	38.62
512	14012.20	14002.70	8632.40	38.392
1024	30909.90	27220.40	19104.85	38.19

This is the improvement brought by the proposed architecture. Also, Table 5 shows a 38% power reduction on an average which can be a considerably good improvement. Thus, the proposed processing element, NHPE and therefore the proposed SCD have shown a reduction in area and power compared to the available decoders. Table 6 shows the hardware performance of the proposed decoder. The performance of the proposed model was compared to other existing architectures at the same code length and code rate. It was evident that the performance of the proposed decoder is competent with the other existing decoders and can provide even better implementation results. The proposed decoder produced better hardware efficiency [23] among the other models and also good normalized throughput. The technology scaled normalized throughput (TNST) helps to compare the throughput across various technologies and is defined by [24],

$$\text{TNST} = \left(\frac{\text{Throughput}}{\text{Gate Count}} \right) * \left(\frac{\text{Technology}}{\text{Target Technology}} \right) \quad (8)$$

This helps to scale the throughput based on the target technology. From Tables 4, 5, and 6, it is evident that the proposed decoder stands out in significantly when compared to the state-of-the-art architectures in terms of low area, low power and higher efficiency without altering the performance. Hence, they can be used for area and power-efficient communication applications.

Table 6. Hardware performance of decoder with code length, N=1024

Design	Yuan and Parhi [4]	Leroux <i>et al.</i> [25]	Kim <i>et al.</i> [6]	Proposed
Message form	LLR	LLR	LLR	LLR
Code rate	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Tech. (nm)	65	65	40	45
Quantization (bits)	6	5	5	5
Frequency (Mhz)	390	500	1000	400
Latency (clock cycles)	1056	2080	1023	1023
Area (μm^2)	355478.48	308693	587070	300717.77
Throughput (Mbps)	378	123	500	490
TNST	2	1.65	3.03	3.1
Efficiency (Mbps/ mm^2)	1064	398	851.78	1633

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a low power, area-efficient architecture for SCD was proposed. a new hybrid processing element was presented, which occupies less area and has low power consumption compared to existing architectures. The proposed processing element was used as the basic building block to construct the decoder. Also, the proposed architecture had better efficiency, which is also a significant feature. The proposed architecture can be combined with look-ahead techniques to further reduce the latency and speed up the decoder. The analysis and implementation conclude that the proposed decoder has inimitable benefits in terms of area and power. The proposed decoder has an error-free approach and finds application in the high-speed communication system, including 5G.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank Visvesvaraya Ph.D. Scheme (VISPHDMEITY-1713), Ministry of electronics and information technology (MeiTY), Government of India for funding this research, and SMDP-C2SD and DST-FIST (Grant number: DST/ETI-324/2012), Government of India for providing the lab facilities.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Arikian, "Channel polarization: A method for constructing capacity-achieving codes for symmetric binary-input memoryless channels," *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 55, no. 7, pp. 3051–3073, 2009, doi: 10.1109/TIT.2009.2021379.
- [2] B. Yuan and K. K. Parhi, "Low-latency successive-cancellation polar decoder architectures using 2-bit decoding," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 61, no. 4, pp. 1241–1254, 2014, doi: 10.1109/TCSI.2013.2283779.
- [3] C. Leroux, I. Tal, A. Vardy, and W. J. Gross, "Hardware architectures for successive cancellation decoding of polar codes," in *2011 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 2011, pp. 1665–1668, doi: 10.1109/ICASSP.2011.5946819.
- [4] B. Yuan and K. K. Parhi, "LLR-based successive-cancellation list decoder for polar codes with multibit decision," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, vol. 64, no. 1, pp. 21–25, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TCSII.2016.2546904.
- [5] P. Giard, G. Sarkis, C. Thibeault, and W. J. Gross, "Multi-mode unrolled architectures for polar decoders," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 63, no. 9, pp. 1443–1453, Sep. 2016, doi: 10.1109/TCSI.2016.2586218.
- [6] C. Kim, H. Yun, S. Ajaz, and H. Lee, "High-throughput low-complexity successive-cancellation polar decoder architecture using one's complement scheme," *JSTS:Journal of Semiconductor Technology and Science*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 427–435, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.5573/JSTS.2015.15.3.427.
- [7] H. R. Yun and H. Lee, "Simplified merged processing element for successive-cancellation polar decoder," *Electronics Letters*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 270–272, 2016, doi: 10.1049/el.2015.3432.
- [8] P. Giard *et al.*, "PolarBear: A 28-nm FD-SOI ASIC for decoding of polar codes," *IEEE Journal on Emerging and Selected Topics in Circuits and Systems*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 616–629, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1109/JETCAS.2017.2745704.
- [9] A. Balatsoukas-Stimming, P. Giard, and A. Burg, "Comparison of polar decoders with existing low-density parity-check and turbo decoders," in *2017 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference Workshops (WCNCW)*, 2017, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/WCNCW.2017.7919106.
- [10] O. Dizdar and E. Arikian, "A high-throughput energy-efficient implementation of successive cancellation decoder for polar codes using combinational logic," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 63, no. 3, pp. 436–447, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1109/TCSI.2016.2525020.
- [11] D. Le, X. Wu, and X. Niu, "Decoding schedule generating method for successive-cancellation decoder of polar codes," *IET Communications*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 462–467, 2016, doi: 10.1049/iet-com.2015.0881.
- [12] C. Gao, R. Liu, B. Dai, and X. Han, "Path splitting selecting strategy-aided successive cancellation list algorithm for polar codes," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 422–425, 2019, doi: 10.1109/LCOMM.2019.2894150.

- [13] S. A. Hashemi, C. Condo, F. Ercan, and W. J. Gross, "Memory-efficient polar decoders," *IEEE Journal on Emerging and Selected Topics in Circuits and Systems*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 604–615, 2017, doi: 10.1109/JETCAS.2017.2764421.
- [14] P. Shi, W. Tang, S. Zhao, and B. Wang, "Performance of polar codes on wireless communication channels," *International Conference on Communication Technology Proceedings, ICCT*, pp. 1134–1138, 2012, doi: 10.1109/ICCT.2012.6511367.
- [15] B. Li, D. Tse, K. Chen, and H. Shen, "Capacity-achieving rateless polar codes," *IEEE International Symposium on Information Theory - Proceedings*, vol. 2016-Augus, pp. 46–50, 2016, doi: 10.1109/ISIT.2016.7541258.
- [16] S. N. Hong, D. Hui, and I. Maric, "Capacity-achieving rate-compatible polar codes," *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 63, no. 12, pp. 7620–7632, 2017, doi: 10.1109/TIT.2017.2756668.
- [17] B. Feng, Q. Zhang, and J. Jiao, "An efficient rateless scheme based on the extendibility of systematic polar codes," *IEEE Access*, vol. 5, pp. 23223–23232, 2017, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2762363.
- [18] J. Kim and J. Lee, "Polar codes for non-identically distributed channels," *Eurasip Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking*, vol. 2016, no. 1, 2016, doi: 10.1186/s13638-016-0782-2.
- [19] A. Mishra *et al.*, "A successive cancellation decoder ASIC for a 1024-bit polar code in 180nm CMOS," *Proceedings - 2012 IEEE Asian Solid-State Circuits Conference, A-SSCC*, pp. 205–208, 2012, doi: 10.1109/IPEC.2012.6522661.
- [20] C. Leroux, A. J. Raymond, G. Sarkis, I. Tal, A. Vardy, and W. J. Gross, "Hardware implementation of successive-cancellation decoders for polar codes," *Journal of Signal Processing Systems*, vol. 69, no. 3, pp. 305–315, 2012, doi: 10.1007/s11265-012-0685-3.
- [21] J.-H. Po, S.-J. Chen, and C. Yu, "Variable code length soft-output decoder of polar codes," in *2015 IEEE International Conference on Digital Signal Processing (DSP)*, 2015, pp. 655–658, doi: 10.1109/ICDSP.2015.7251956.
- [22] C. Zhang and K. K. Parhi, "Low-latency sequential and overlapped architectures for successive cancellation polar decoder," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 61, no. 10, pp. 2429–2441, 2013, doi: 10.1109/tsp.2013.2251339.
- [23] H.-Y. Hsu, A.-Y. Wu, and J.-C. Yeo, "Area-efficient VLSI design of reed–solomon decoder for 10GBase-LX4 optical communication systems," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, vol. 53, no. 11, pp. 1245–1249, Nov. 2006, doi: 10.1109/TCSII.2006.882360.
- [24] M. Bohr, "A 30 year retrospective on dennard's MOSFET scaling paper," *IEEE Solid-State Circuits Newsletter*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 11–13, 2007, doi: 10.1109/N-SSC.2007.4785534.
- [25] C. Leroux, A. J. Raymond, G. Sarkis, and W. J. Gross, "A Semi-parallel successive-cancellation decoder for polar codes," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 61, no. 2, pp. 289–299, 2013, doi: 10.1109/TSP.2012.2223693.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Sujanth Roy James is currently pursuing his doctoral research at National Institute of technology Tiruchirappalli. His area of research includes digital architecture design, ASIC Design and FPGA based system design. He is currently working on design of FPGA architectures for decoders used in Polar codes. He can be contacted at email: sujanthroyj@gmail.com.

Lakshminarayanan Gopalakrishnan is a Professor in the Dept of Electronics and Communication Engineering at NIT-Trichy, India. His research expertise are primarily in the areas of Wireless System Design in VLSI / Physical Layer Design, Cognitive Radio algorithms and techniques. He is carrying out research work in VLSI Signal Processing, FPGA based Wireless Transceivers and Reconfigurable systems He served in one of the VLSI design companies, Sasken Communication Technologies Limited, Bangalore and was involved in the project "FPGA implementation of USB Sub System". He is holding one patent and filed another one. He can be contacted at email: laksh@nitt.edu.